

Original Article

INFLUENCE OF ORGANIZATION CONFLICT ON PERFORMANCE OF BUSINESS EDUCATORS IN UNIVERSITIES IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

The need to enhance job performance among Nigerian workforce, especially business educators, informed this study to determine the influence of organizational conflicts on performance of business educators in universities in Enugu State. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population for the study comprised 27 Business Educators in all three Universities in the State. The instrument used for data collection was 18-item four-point rating scale questionnaire developed by the researchers and titled influence of organizational conflicts on the performance of business educators in universities in enugu state. The instrument was validated by three experts; two from the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education and one from Measurement and Evaluation unit of the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education both in the Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient which yielded 0.78. Out of 27 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 26 copies were retrieved and used for data analysis representing 96.30% return rate. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test was used to test the three null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at 74 degree of freedom. The study revealed that Business Educators agreed to the items under interpersonal conflicts, technological conflicts and structural conflicts among Business Educators in universities in Enugu State. Based on the findings, some implications were deduced and it was recommended among others that the Institutions should establish clear guidelines for the fair distribution of resources, including technological tools and funding, to reduce competition and related conflicts. Also, revisiting organizational hierarchies and reward systems, as well as structural issues that hinder collaboration and satisfaction, fostering a more cohesive work environment among Business Educators in Universities in Enugu State should be done by the University administration.

Keywords: Business Education, Organizational conflict, Business Educators and influence.

INTRODUCTION

In the dynamic realm of higher education, organizational conflicts stand as a significant determinant of institutional functioning and effectiveness. Within the context of universities, where educators are entrusted with the responsibility of shaping the next generation of business leaders, the prevalence and impact of organizational conflict among them. These conflicts can arise from different factors and can significantly shape students educational experiences and learning outcomes. Organizations are structured social entities composed of individuals or groups working together to achieve common goals. They can take various forms, such as businesses, government agencies, non-profit organizations, educational institutions, and more. Jones (2016) defined an organization as a group of people working together in a structured and coordinated way to achieve specific goal. Jones (2016) further emphasized that organizations are collaborative and goal-oriented in nature which highlights the importance of coordination and structure in every organization. In opinion of Daft (2018), organization is a social entity that is goal-directed, designed as deliberately structured and coordinated activity systems, and linked to the external environment. According to Daft, organizations are purposeful entities with structured processes aimed at achieving specific objectives.

In organizations such as universities, human beings interact consistently in different ways towards the achievement of organizational goals paving way for disagreements which may lead to conflicts. Conflict is a natural and pervasive aspect of human interactions, occurring when individuals or groups experience discord or disagreement due to differences in interests, values, goals, perceptions, or beliefs. Olaopa, (2016). Conceptualized conflict as a natural and inevitable disagreement or discord arising from differences in interests, values, perceptions, or goals among individuals or groups

within a social system. Furthermore, Oloko-Oba (2018) averred that conflict is a social phenomenon characterized by disagreements, disputes, or clashes resulting from perceived or actual differences in interests, needs, beliefs, or values among individuals, groups, or organizations. In summary, conflict is dynamic in nature and can manifest in various forms such as disagreements, disputes, clashes, or tensions rooted in perceived or actual differences in interests, needs, beliefs, or values.

According to Deutsch, (2014), organizational conflict is the processes by which differences in goals and opinions lead to disputes among members of a group in an organization. Jehn (2019) explained that organizational conflict occurs when there is discord or disagreement between groups or individuals within an organization, which can arise from differences in goals, perspectives, or values, In essence, organizational conflict is a phenomenon within an organization characterized by discord or disagreement among groups or individuals, stemming from differences in goals, perspectives, or values. This conflict arises as a result of the processes through which variations in goals and opinions among members of a group or organization lead to disputes and tension within the organizational context.

Organizational conflict is a pervasive phenomenon in academic institutions that can significantly impact the working environment, faculty morale, and the overall quality of education. Universities in Enugu State, like many educational institutions globally, face challenges related to conflicts among their faculty members in different fields including Business Educators. These conflicts can arise from a variety of sources such as differences in academic goals, power tussles, limited resources, administrative decisions, and interpersonal dynamics. Omisore and Abiodun (2017), opined that interpersonal conflicts are commonly influenced by personal incompatibilities, communication barriers,

and varying viewpoints. These factors can create significant friction, particularly when educators have differing approaches to pedagogy or priorities within the department leading to reduced teamwork and a negative impact on student outcomes.

Likewise, technological conflicts stem from issues such as resistance to new technologies, disparities in technological expertise, and differences in the adoption of digital tools. Klein and Knight (2019) averred that technological conflicts can arise from disparities in tech adoption across teams where some employees may resist integrating new technology due to a lack of understanding or comfort, which creates tension between technologically inclined and resistant staff. Furthermore, Lee and Xia (2021) posited that technological conflicts in educational institutions arise because, noting that some educators resist digital teaching tools, especially when proper training is not provided. This often leads to frustrations and conflict among educators who perceive it as unequal support in their professional development.

Furthermore, structural conflicts often emerge from hierarchical and organizational frameworks within universities, where the distribution of resources and roles can be considered to be inequitable. Rahim and Katz (2020) discussed structural conflicts as conflicts that arise from rigid departmental structures and unequal distribution of resources. In academic institutions, issues like imbalanced workload distribution and unclear decision-making processes can heighten tension among educators. Brown and Roloff (2021), explained that structural conflicts deter on professional collaboration and performance in academic settings. The authors observed that conflicts arising from poorly defined roles or inconsistent departmental policies disrupt collaboration and create an environment where educators may feel unsupported or undervalued. For Business Educators, mismanagement in resource allocation or unclear communication from

administrative bodies can escalate structural conflicts, affecting both job satisfaction and educational quality.

Business Educators are individuals who teach courses related to business disciplines such as accounting, finance, marketing, management, and economics at educational institutions, including universities, colleges, and vocational schools (Bong, and Park, 2023). According to Egglund (2019), Business Educators encompass a diverse group of professionals who specialize in teaching business-related subjects at various levels of education, including secondary schools, community colleges, and universities.

Universities are tertiary institutions for higher learning. Adegbite (2018), saw universities as "comprehensive learning communities that serve as hubs for knowledge dissemination, critical thinking, cultural exchange, and skills development, contributing to national development and global competitiveness. Contributing, Nwosu (2019) described universities as centers of academic excellence, research innovation, and intellectual discourse, fostering a conducive environment for lifelong learning, social integration, and the advancement of human capital. Invariably, universities are vibrant institutions that foster knowledge creation, critical thinking, cultural understanding, and skills development. Universities drive national development, enhancing global competitiveness, and advancing human capital through academic excellence, research innovation, and lifelong learning opportunities. In Nigeria, universities are categorized into two main types: private and public. Based on their ownership, funding and governance.

Public universities are institutions of higher education that are primarily funded and operated by the government (Federal and State). They play vital role in providing affordable and accessible education to diverse range of students, contributing to societal

development, research advancements, and economic growth. Public universities are educational institutions established and funded by the government to provide accessible higher education to the general public. They play crucial role in fostering regional development and innovation through research, technology transfer, and workforce development (Kielbowicz, 2018). On the other hand, private universities, also known as independent or non-public universities, are higher education institutions that are privately funded and operated. Private universities often have their own governing boards and rely on tuition fees, donations, and endowments to support their operations and programs (Baum and Ma 2017). According to Chen and Bastedo (2019), private universities often have smaller student's population compared to public universities, allowing for smaller class sizes and potentially fostering more intimate learning environment. They may also have greater flexibility in curriculum design and program offerings, enabling them to be more responsive to industrial needs and emerging disciplines.

Many public and private universities in Nigeria offer Business Education programme handled by Business Educators and there is bound to be organizational conflicts among them in the course of discharging their duties. These conflicts may influence their performance effectiveness towards the achievement of the goal and objectives of the programme.

Influence refers to the ability or power of a person (or thing) to impact the thoughts, behaviors, decisions, or actions of others. Smith (2016) defined influence as the capacity or power to affect the thoughts, behaviors, decisions, or actions of others, either directly or indirectly, through persuasion, authority, expertise, or social connections. According to Ahmed (2019) influence is the ability to inspire, motivate, or guide others towards specific outcomes, goals, or behaviors, leveraging personal charisma, communication skills, and leadership

qualities. Summarily, influence involves the ability to shape and direct the thoughts, behaviors, decisions, or actions of others through various means such as persuasion, authority, expertise, social connections, personal charisma, communication skills, and leadership qualities.

Business Educators in universities in Enugu State may experience conflicts due to competition for limited resources (e.g., funding, office space, teaching materials among others) because unequal access to resources and differences in hierarchical positions can lead to organizational tensions, impacting educators' morale, collaboration, and job satisfaction, hence this study.

This research was anchored on Conflict Theory by Karl Marx, (1959). The theory posits that conflict arises from inequalities in power and resources within a social structure. This theory argues that groups with differing access to resources or authority naturally come into conflict as they compete to protect or increase their respective advantages. Therefore, this theory is relevant to this study as it helps to explain the root causes of structural, interpersonal, and resource-based conflicts among business educators in universities in Enugu State. The theory also sheds light on how institutional practices, such as the allocation of resources or decision-making processes may either escalate or help mitigate conflicts

Statement of the Problem

Business Education programs play crucial roles in preparing students for careers in various fields of commerce, management, and economics. However, the presence of organizational conflict among Business Educators in different universities can undermine their ability to fulfill their educational mission and objectives. Organizational conflicts occur among business educators in Enugu State due to competition for limited resources (e.g., funding, office space, teaching materials etc), unequal access to resources and differences in hierarchical positions

as well as decision-making processes and other factors. These negatively impact their morale, collaboration, and job satisfaction. Understanding interpersonal, technological and structural conflicts within these educational settings is essential for developing effective conflict management strategies, improving faculty collaboration, and enhancing educational outcomes.

This made it imperative to conduct this study to determine the influence of organizational conflicts on the performance of business educators in the universities in order to provide empirical data for objective remedial actions by relevant stakeholders.

Purpose of the Study

The main objective of the study was to determine the influence of organizational conflicts among business educators in universities in Enugu State on their performance. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the influence of interpersonal conflicts among Business Educators in universities in Enugu State on their performance.
2. Ascertain influence of technological conflicts among Business Educators in universities in Enugu State on their performance.
3. Determine influence of structural conflicts among Business Educators in universities in Enugu State on their performance.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the influence of interpersonal conflicts among Business Educators in universities Enugu State on their performance?
2. What are the influences of technological conflicts among Business Educators in universities Enugu State on their performance?
3. What are the influences of structural conflicts among Business Educators in universities Enugu State on their performance?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant.

1. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the influence of interpersonal conflicts among Business Educators in universities in Enugu State on their performance.

2. There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female respondents on the influence of technological conflicts among Business Educators in universities in Enugu State on their performance.

3. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the influences of structural conflict among Business Educators in universities in Enugu State on their performance.

Methodology

The researcher adopted descriptive survey research design since it involved eliciting information from respondents. According to Jim, Nwokike and Ezeabii (2017), in Ezeabii, Ekoh-Nweke and Aribido (2023), descriptive survey research design is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from a few people or entire group. The study was carried out in Enugu State which is one of the states in South-East Nigeria.

The population of the study comprises of 27 Business Educators three universities in the state (federal 20, state 6 and private 1) the entire population was studied without sampling because the size was small. A structured questionnaire titled Influence of Organization Conflict on performance of Business Educators Questionnaire (IOCPBEQ). And containing 18 items in three clusters of six items each was used for data collection. The questionnaire was structured in 4-points rating scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree. The instrument was validated by three experts; two from the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education and one from Measurement and Evaluation unit of the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education both in the Faculty of

Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu. The instrument was trial-tested using 10 copies of the instrument on Business Educators in universities Eboyi State Nigeria. The justification for using Eboyi State is that the Business Educators in the state use the same NUC curriculum hence similar educational policy with universities in Enugu State. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient which yielded 0.78. Out of 27 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 26 copies were retrieved and used for data analysis representing 96.30% return rate. Mean

and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test was used to test the three null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at 74 degree of freedom. Three research assistants who were briefed on the modalities helped in the administration of the instrument. Out of 27 copies of the instrument distributed, 26 were retrieved giving 96.29 percent return rate. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The decision was based on a cut-off mean score of 2.50 in relation to the cluster mean score.

Results

Table 1: Mean score and Standard Deviation of male and female business educators on the interpersonal conflicts among Business Educators in universities Enugu State N= 26

N	interpersonal conflicts among Business Educators in universities includes;	Male N=10		Female N=16		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
1	Interpersonal conflicts between business educators often arise due to differing teaching philosophies.	3.65	0.49	3.30	0.70	3.44	0.64	Agree
2	Competition for resources (e.g., research funding, teaching materials) is a major cause of conflict among business educators.	3.25	0.64	3.13	0.68	3.18	0.66	Agree
3	Personality differences between business educators frequently lead to interpersonal conflicts in the workplace	3.40	0.60	3.03	0.67	3.18	0.66	Agree
4	Interpersonal conflicts among business educators negatively impact the overall quality of education provided to students.	3.30	0.66	3.20	0.66	3.24	0.65	Agree
5	Unresolved interpersonal conflicts among members decrease morale and job satisfaction within the department.	3.45	0.51	3.27	0.74	3.34	0.66	Agree
6	Interpersonal conflicts among business educators create a hostile work environment that affects professional collaboration.	3.30	0.80	3.17	0.53	3.22	0.65	Agree
Cluster Mean/SD		3.39	0.62	3.18	0.66	3.27	0.65	Agree

Table 1, shows that the mean ratings of the items range from 3.18 of 3.44 are above the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This indicates that the respondents agreed with the items as causes of interpersonal conflicts among Business Educators in universities in Enugu State. This is confirmed by the overall cluster mean score of 3.27. Standard deviations for all the items for the two groups

are within the same range which implies that the respondents are homogeneous in their mean ratings.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on the interpersonal conflict among Business Educators in universities Enugu State.

Table 2: Summary of t-test Analysis of male and female respondents' mean scores on causes and influence of interpersonal conflicts on the performance of Business Educators in universities Enugu State

Variables	N	T	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	10	1.036	24	.147	2.40000	1.17851	NS
Female	16						

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Table 2 shows that p-value of 0.147 was recorded at 48 degrees of freedom and the t-value of 1.036 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female respondents on the causes and influence

of interpersonal conflicts among Business Educators in universities Enugu State and their performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected one is hereby retained.

Table 3: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of male and female business educators on technological conflicts among Business Educators in universities Enugu State N= 26

S/N	technological conflicts among Business Educators in universities include;	Male N=10		Female N=16		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
7	Technological differences in teaching methods (e.g., online vs. traditional methods) often lead to conflicts among business educators.	3.20	0.83	3.07	0.78	3.12	0.80	Agree
8	Conflicts arise when business educators are expected to adopt new technologies without adequate training or support.	3.00	0.79	2.80	0.66	2.88	0.72	Agree
9	Conflicts occur when some business educators are resistant to integrating new technologies into their teaching practices	2.95	0.60	3.03	0.89	3.00	0.78	Agree
10	Business educators who prefer traditional teaching methods experience conflict with those who advocate for more technology integration.	2.80	0.83	2.83	0.79	2.82	0.80	Agree
11	The unequal access to technological resources within the department causes tension among business educators	3.20	0.70	2.90	0.80	3.02	0.77	Agree
12	Conflicts occur when some business educators are resistant to integrating new technologies into their teaching practices.	2.95	0.76	2.93	0.69	2.94	0.71	Agree
Cluster Mean/SD		2.97	0.76	2.93	0.77	2.97	0.76	Agree

Data presented in Table 3 indicates that items have an overall item mean ratings for items ranges from 2.82 to 3.12 depicting agree. This implies that the items are the technological conflicts among Business Educators in universities Enugu State. The overall cluster mean rating of 2.97 shows agree. This implies that the items are the technological conflicts among Business Educators in universities Enugu

State. The low standard deviation of 0.71 shows that the respondent’s opinions do not differ remarkably to the itemized.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female Business Educators on the technological conflict among Business Educators in universities Enugu State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test Analysis of mean response scores of male and female business educators on the technological conflict among Business Educators in universities Enugu State

Variables	N	T	Df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Difference	Error	Decision
Male	10	.106	24	.916	.15000	1.41228		NS
Female	16							

The data obtained from the in Table 4 shows the summary of independent t-test analysis. The p-value of 0.916 was recorded at 48 degrees of freedom and the t-value of 0.106. The p-value of 0.916 is more than the alpha value of 0.05 level of significance. As the significant value of 0.916 is more than the 0.05

alpha value the null hypothesis is not significant. This implies that there is no significant difference with respect to the items on the mean response scores of male and female business educators on the technological conflict among Business Educators in universities Enugu State. Therefore, the null

hypothesis two is hereby retained.

Table 5: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of the male and female business educators on the structural conflicts among Business Educators in universities N=2

S/N	structural conflicts among Business Educators in universities are as follows;	Male N=10		Female N= 16		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
13	The organizational hierarchy creates barriers to effective communication among Business Educators.	3.50	0.51	3.30	0.70	3.38	0.68	Agree
14	The distribution of resources (e.g., funding, office space, technology) among Business Educators is often unequal and leads to conflicts	3.25	0.55	3.27	0.58	3.26	0.56	Agree
15	The decision-making process in the department is unclear and leads to misunderstandings among Business Educators.	3.05	0.69	3.17	0.69	3.12	0.69	Agree
16	Workload distribution among Business Educators in my department is unfair, resulting in structural conflicts.	2.65	0.67	2.83	0.59	2.76	0.62	Agree
17	The reward and recognition system is biased, which causes tension and conflicts among Business Educators.	3.10	0.79	3.07	0.69	3.08	0.72	Agree
18	Limited opportunities for collaboration and team work among business educators.	2.70	0.66	2.97	0.72	2.86	0.70	Agree
Cluster Mean/SD		3.04	0.65	3.10	0.66	3.08	0.66	Agree

Data presented in Table 3 shows the summary mean ratings for item 13 to 18. The items mean rating ranges from 2.76 to 3.38 depicting agree. This implies that the items are the structural conflicts among Business Educators in universities Enugu State. The overall cluster mean rating of 3.08 indicates agree. This implies that the itemized are the structural conflicts among Business Educators in

universities Enugu State. The low standard deviation of 0.56 indicates that the respondent’s opinions do not differ remarkably to the itemized.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female Business Educators on the structural conflict among Business Educators in universities Enugu State.

Table 6: Summary of t-test Analysis of mean response scores of male and female business educators on the structural conflicts among Business Educators in universities Enugu State

Variables	N	T	Df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	10	.154	24	.878	.18333	1.19134	NS
Female	16						

The data obtained from the t-test analysis in Table 6 shows the summary of independent t-test analysis.

The p-value of 0.878 was recorded at 48 degrees of freedom and the t-value of 0.154. The p-value of

0.878 is more than the alpha value of 0.05 level of significance. Since the significant value of .878 is more than the 0.05 alpha values the null hypothesis is not significant. This implies that there is no significant difference with respect to the items on the mean response scores of male and female Business Educators on the structural conflicts among Business Educators in universities Enugu State. Therefore, null hypothesis three is hereby retained.

Discussion

Findings of the study showed that there are three key causative factors for interpersonal conflicts among business educators in universities in Enugu State and that these conflicts have negative influence on their performance. This finding is in agreement with the view of Omisore and Abiodun (2017) which noted that interpersonal conflicts are commonly influenced by personal incompatibilities, communication barriers, and varying viewpoints and that such can lead to reduced teamwork and a negative impact on student outcomes.

In addition, the findings of the research indicate that respondents agreed with the six items under technological conflicts among Business Educators in universities in Enugu State. Conflicts stem from disparities in teaching approaches, like online versus traditional methods, lack of adequate training for new technologies, and unequal access to technological resources. The cluster mean rating of 2.97 shows agreement on these issues, suggesting a resistance to rapid technological adoption and an insufficient technological infrastructure. This is in agreement with the study of Klein and Knight, (2019), which suggested that organizations implement training programs to support technologies adoption and reduce conflicts.

More also, the findings of the study indicates that respondents agreed with the six items under structural conflicts among Business Educators in universities in Enugu State. These items include: organizational hierarchy, resource distribution, limited opportunity for collaboration, decision

making, reward and recognition and workload allocation, are also significant sources of conflict among Business Educators. The mean ratings for these items range from 2.76 to 3.38, indicating agreement on these factors. This is in agreement with the opinion of Rahim and Katz (2020), the authors opined structural conflicts as conflicts that arise from rigid departmental structures and unequal distribution of resources. In academic institutions, issues like imbalanced workload distribution and unclear decision-making processes can heighten tension among educators. Business educators, for instance, may feel that workload assignments or resource allocations are unfairly managed, leading to feelings of frustration and resentment.

Conclusion

The study found that different interpersonal, technological, and structural factors are responsible for conflicts among Business Educators in universities in Enugu State and that these conflicts have negative influence on their performance. Based on the findings, it was concluded that if sources of conflicts among these professionals are reduced or eliminated, their performance will improve, thereby enhancing student outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Management of the universities should implement training programs focused on conflict resolution strategies to help business educators manage interpersonal and structural conflicts effectively for enhanced performance.
2. University management should establish clear guidelines for the fair distribution of resources, including technological tools and funding, to reduce competition and related conflicts.
3. Leadership of Business Education Department in the universities should revisit organizational hierarchies and reward systems to address structural issues that hinder collaboration

and satisfaction among lectures to foster a more cohesive work environment for enhanced performance.

4. The university management should provide regular workshops and support for technological tools to help business educators' transition to new teaching methods with less friction. Training in online platforms and digital tools would bridge the gap between traditional and modern teaching practices

5. The Head of Business Education Department should create channels for open communication and collaborative decision-making to help lecturers feel more included in departmental decisions, potentially reducing structural conflicts for effective performance.

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